

MODELLING OF TEXTILE COMPOSITES WITH VARIABLE STIFFNESS

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ABSTRACT

Functional composite materials allowing stiffness reduction upon external stimulation are being developed within the European projects ENLIGHT and SafeEV. The aim is to develop material concepts to reduce the severity of injuries involving vulnerable road users. The current work addresses the development of textile composite material models aimed to be employed in a car front structure during static loading to low velocity impact situations. The modelled material is a non-crimp fabric reinforced thermoplastic (LPET) composite, in which the stiffness reduction relies on resistive heating of the carbon reinforcement upon application of electric current through the fibres. The stiffness reduction is achieved by a phase transformation of the thermoplastic matrix material.

In this paper it is shown how a micro- and mesomodelling methodology in concert with only a few simple DMTA measurements can be utilized to model the macroscopic stiffness response of an impacted beam at various temperatures and loading rates. The material models used for simulation of the material show a good correlation with the experimental data despite the exclusion of a damage model and failing to account for the temperature variation within the specimens used in the experimental testing. The peak loads are well predicted.

1 INTRODUCTION

The most frequent areas of injuries in pedestrian fatalities are the head and the lower extremities, and the vehicle area causing these injuries is usually the front of the car. The severity of head injuries upon car front impact depends mainly on impact speed and the vehicle's frontal stiffness. To address the latter, functional composite materials allowing stiffness reduction upon external stimulation are therefore being developed within the European projects ENLIGHT and SafeEV. Implementation of such technology in the design of a car front has high potential to result in increased protection of vulnerable road users (VRUs), by decreasing the deceleration forces experienced by the VRUs. Materials with adjustable stiffness have been studied in recent years mainly for applications in aerospace industry, such as morphing wings or deployable structures. The studied concepts rely on shape-memory alloys and polymers, as well as electroactive polymers, piezoelectric and magnetostrictive materials [1], [2].

The use of resistive heating upon application of an electric current through carbon fibres to achieve a phase transformation within a composite material, and thereby a stiffness reduction, has been studied by Bismarck and co-workers. Two different concepts relying on this mechanism were studied: (i) a thermoplastic interphase between a thermoset matrix and its carbon fibre reinforcement [3] and (ii) thermoplastic layers in a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy laminate [4]. These concepts were designed to combine the good mechanical performance of thermoset resins with the large potential for stiffness-reduction of thermoplastics. In [5] a stiffness variable composite material was obtained by coating carbon fibres with a thermoplastic polymer in a continuous process, followed by infusion with an epoxy resin. A drastic decrease in transverse stiffness could be detected for the composite material

when the temperature was increased above the glass transition temperature of the thermoplastic interphase.

Alongside the material developments, appropriate material models being able to predict the mechanical response of the stiffness variable composite are needed. The current work therefore addresses the development of textile composite material models aimed to be employed in a car front structure during static loading to low velocity impact situations. The laminate stiffness is homogenised based on properties of modelled representative volume elements (RVEs). Using a bottom-up approach, i.e. starting with fibre and matrix properties, the mechanical response of the textile composite is modelled at different temperatures. Low velocity impact tests are also performed with the material in both softened and glassy state, and then simulated in order to validate the modelling methodology. These tests are made in a drop test rig modified to allow for the softening of the material upon application of an electric current through the carbon fibres.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Composite preparation

Thermoplastic non-crimp fabric (NCF) composites were manufactured using dry NCF preforms consisting of Tenax HTS 12k carbon fibre rovings with a small amount of E-glass in warp direction and a combi yarn in weft direction. This is actually a uniweave, but due to its similarities with NCFs we will in the following refer to it as a unidirectional (UD) NCF. The dry preforms were alternately stacked together with LPET preforms (COMFIL 30114-13, 130 g/m² LPET plain weave), placed in vacuum-bags and in an autoclave at 6 bar pressure. The temperature was ramped up to 230°C during 3 h and then cooled down during 2 h to 100°C before removing it from the autoclave to create:

- [(±45)₃]_s laminate: 12 layers of carbon fibre and 13 layers of LPET. Final thickness 3.2 mm.
- UD NCF composite: 4 layers of carbon fibre and 5 layers of LPET. Final thickness 1 mm.
- A plate of neat LPET was also produced to be analysed using DMTA.

Average fibre volume fraction of the composite laminates was estimated by relating it to the weave areal weight and thickness of the plate according to:

$$V_f = \frac{A_w n}{t \rho_f} \quad (1)$$

where A_w is fibre areal weight (mass per area per ply), n is the number of plies, t is measured thickness and ρ_f the fibre density. Excluding the resin rich uneven surface layer from the peel-ply, a fibre volume fraction of approximately $V_f = 0.55$ was obtained for both composites.

2.2 Material characterization

DMTA measurements on neat LPET and in the transverse direction of the NCF composite were performed on a Rheometric Scientific DMTA 4 analyzer in single cantilever bending mode. The free distance between the clamp and the drive shaft was 14 mm. To investigate the stiffness dependence on both temperature and loading rate, rectangular samples with approximate dimensions 30x10x1 mm were heated from room temperature to 105°C with increments of 10°C (soak time for each temperature step was 5 min). The tests were performed in strain controlled mode with frequencies 0.3, 1, 5 and 30 Hz and with a maximum strain of 0.05%. The specimens were clamped to the frame with an initial clamp torque of 30 cNm. The results from the neat LPET analysis were used when modelling the NCF composite stiffness during the low velocity impact.

2.3 Impact testing with applied current

The stiffness-modifiable properties of the material were verified by impact tests with applied current using a 3-point bending test setup in a drop weight test rig. Specimens with approximate

dimensions of 25×3.2 mm (width×thickness) were simply supported between two rounded supports with a radius of 5 mm and a span of 50 mm. All specimens were impacted with a mass of 0.975 kg and an impact speed of 3.12 m/s, resulting in a kinetic energy of around 4.8 J. The impactor tup was a steel cylinder with a radius of 5 mm, see Fig. 1. During impact the force was recorded using a Dytran 1203V5 piezoelectric ring sensor. The deflection of the underside of the specimen was recorded using a MEL M70LL/10 laser distance sensor. The speed of the impactor just before impact was registered using a photo sensor which recorded the passing of a photo flag impactor.

The specimens were connected to a DC power supply and voltages of 2-4 were applied while monitoring the temperature using an IR-camera. When the desired temperature was reached and stable, the voltage was turned off and the specimen was impacted immediately after.

Figure 1: Impact test setup

3 MATERIAL MODELLING

3.1 Effective UD NCF stiffness properties

NCF composites are heterogeneous materials with a quasi-laminar structure, each lamina consisting of theoretically straight fibre tows with distinct orientation and resin “cylinders” with complex cross-sections aligned parallel to them. Unfortunately, the fibre tows have certain out-of-plane waviness which together with the complex cross-section features makes accurate prediction of the NCF composite stiffness a rather difficult task. To make the problem solvable, idealisations of the mesostructure have been made to convert the original geometrical features (bundle cross-section shape/size and 0° tow waviness parameters such as wavelength and amplitude) into effective properties of the idealised structure. The properties calculations have been simplified by performing homogenisation separately on both micro- and meso length scales. On microscale the homogenisation is over the fibre and matrix microstructure within the bundle. It was performed using the Composite Cylinder Assemblage (CCA) model with a self-consistent modelling scheme to calculate the transverse shear modulus according to the description by Christensen and Lo [6]. In result, the transversely isotropic elastic properties of the bundle are obtained. For the purpose of having a convenient way of determining the UD bundle stiffness as function of fibre volume fraction directly in the FE-input file, simplified polynomial expressions derived from the micromechanical modelling were then used. On the mesoscale the fibre tows are thus considered as homogeneous materials, and in order to calculate macroscale properties, homogenisation was performed over the mesostructure RVE which consists of an assumed representative mesoelement corresponding to a curved tow surrounded by a thin resin layer and glass fibre threads near the bundle ends, as illustrated by Fig. 2. Actually, the size of the RVE should depend on the periodicity or randomness of the bundle placement in different lamina, including periodicity in the NCF composite thickness direction.

Based on the bundle shape/size characteristics from previous studies using the same NCF the decision has been to model the bundle cross-section bottom up, by placing key-points, connecting

lines and areas to form the shape of a superellipse, see Fig. 2. In the next step the sinusoidal shape of the tow is modelled with its centre line according to:

$$z = A \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}\left(x - \frac{L}{4}\right)\right) = -A \left(\cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{L}\right)\right) \quad (2)$$

For the z -coordinate through the thickness and x -coordinate along the tow. A is amplitude and L wavelength of the tow. Everything is parameterised so that layer thickness, bundle volume fraction, fibre volume fraction in bundles, tow waviness (amplitude and wavelength) and element size may be easily altered. For this composite $A = 0.09$ mm, $L = 5$ mm and layer thickness $t = 0.25$ mm.

Figure 2: Transversely isotropic CF bundle (left) and a curved tow surrounded by a thin resin layer and glass fibre threads near the bundle ends (right).

The mesomechanical study was conducted using the commercial FE-code Ansys. The element type was SOLID45, which is a 3D structural solid element defined by eight nodes having three degrees of freedom at each node. First, a straight tow ($A=0$) was analyzed. A generalized plane strain condition was constructed by coupling of nodes on the free surfaces ensuring that flat surfaces remain flat after deformation. Normal loading was introduced by applying a constant displacement over edge surfaces one at the time in 1, 2 and 3-directions respectively. The moduli in the various directions were calculated by summation of the reaction forces divided by the corresponding cross-section area and applied strain to the RVE. Poisson's ratios were also calculated. The effective stiffness in fibre direction of the curved embedded mesoelement was then analyzed by applying surface elements (SURF154 elements) on the top and bottom surfaces, having an elastic foundation stiffness based on the out-of-plane stiffness (3-direction) of the mesoelement from the previous step.

3.2 Modelling the impact response

The effective (homogenised) NCF composite properties have been used to model the impact response of the $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ laminate at room temperature and at elevated temperature. The unsupported length is 50mm. The composite is modelled using eight node brick (C3D8R) elements in Abaqus/Explicit and normal contact is defined between all surfaces in the model. The supports and the impactor are modelled using rigid elements. For each composite ply within the laminate one layer of elements is used.

Figure 3: FE model setup for 3-point bend impact test.

A VUMAT user subroutine is used to define the non-linear constitutive response of the composite. Within this subroutine, the non-linear portion of the constitutive response is modelled using the equation:

$$\sigma_{NL} = \frac{c}{\gamma} (1 - e^{-\gamma \epsilon_{NL}}) \quad (3)$$

Where NL indicates non-linear and c and γ are parameters used to fit experimental constitutive data (taken from previous in-plane shear tests performed in the ENLIGHT project). These parameters are calibrated for the shear response, with values of 3000 and 90, respectively, at room temperature and 400 and 90, respectively, at 85°C. The finite element model does not account for any damage that may occur in the laminate during testing.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Load rate dependent material properties

The results of the DMTA measurements on neat LPET and in the transverse direction of the NCF composite are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Storage modulus vs time in DMTA test for various constant temperatures.

A screening test (DMTA, 1Hz and 5°C/min) performed earlier in the project showed that T_g onset is approximately 56 °C for the NCF UD composite (tested in transverse direction). Therefore, the temperature in the impact test needs to be higher than that to reduce the stiffness any significant amount. Also, the strain rate in the impact test will be much higher than analyzed by the DMTA test. For instance, 30 Hz testing speed implies that the highest strain rate in the DMTA test is 0.015 s^{-1} . In the impact test the strain rate is approximately 18 s^{-1} for the outer layer calculated using the well known formula for maximum strain in a 3-point bending test.

From Fig. 4 it can be seen that at 75 °C the stiffness reduction may not be sufficiently large at the higher strain rates during impact. Therefore, the LPET modulus estimation was performed for the 85 °C impact test case as well as the room temperature test case. It is assumed that the linear trends at room temperature and for the 85 °C storage modulus vs time curves can be extrapolated to the higher strain rate observed in the impact test (this may be an underestimation of the stiffness). The calculated material properties are shown in Table 1.

Property	Carbon fibre	Glass fibre	LPET (at RT)	LPET (at 85 °C)	UD NCF (at RT)	UD NCF (at 85 °C)
E_1 (GPa)	233	76	2.4	0.44	129	125
E_2 (GPa)	23	76	2.4	0.44	7.93	2.05
E_3 (GPa)	23	76	2.4	0.44	7.56	1.86
G_{12} (GPa)	30	31	0.86	0.16	3.5*	1.9*
G_{13} (GPa)	30	31	0.86	0.16	3.5*	1.9*
G_{23} (GPa)	9.6	31	0.86	0.16	2.62	0.66
ν_{12}	0.2	0.22	0.4	0.4	0.27	0.27
ν_{13}	0.2	0.22	0.4	0.4	0.29	0.29
ν_{23}	0.2	0.22	0.4	0.4	0.48	0.48

Table 1: Fibre (assumed), matrix (estimated from DMTA) and NCF composite properties (calculated) used in impact simulations. *Initial stiffness from previous in-plane shear tests of the same material in the ENLIGHT project.

4.2 Impact tests and simulations

The results of the impact testing of the $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ specimens are shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Measured impact response for the $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ specimens at different temperatures.

For all specimens there is a load peak at a deflection of approximately 2 mm. This is probably related to extensive damage development in the specimens. For the specimens tested at 65 °C and 75 °C the load peaks at 2 mm are similar to the one tested in room temperature. However, the maximum load is significantly smaller, suggesting an increase in damping at these temperatures. A significant stiffness decrease could only be seen when tested at 85 °C.

The temperature was not perfectly distributed over the whole sample, as visualised in Fig. 6. Near the steel supports the temperatures in the specimens are lower due to heat conduction. In the 85 °C impact test the surface temperatures near the supports were about 70 °C. This certainly will have an influence regarding the flexural stiffness of the specimen, effectively resulting in a shorter support span length compared to if the temperature would be 85 °C uniformly distributed over the whole specimen length.

Figure 6: Measured surface temperature of the 85 °C specimen.

Figure 7: Measured and predicted impact response for the $[(\pm 45)_3]_s$ specimens at room temperature and 85 °C.

Figure 7 shows a comparison between the experimentally measured response during the impact test and the results of the FE simulations. The FE simulations did not include damage and assumed the temperature was constant throughout the specimen, which was not the case in the experimental setup. This could explain why the experimental response appears to be stiffer initially. Despite this, the overall responses attained from the simulations show a fairly good agreement with the experimental data and the peak loads at both temperatures are well predicted.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The evaluated material could be shown to reduce its stiffness during impact at elevated temperatures and upon application of current. The implementation of material concept in the design of a car front has high potential to result in increased protection of VRUs, by decreasing the deceleration forces experienced by the VRUs. The material concept may also have potential in applications realising improved vibro-acoustic behaviour. For instance, Finegan & Gibson [7] used a micromechanical model to demonstrate that a coating layer of highly dissipative polymer applied to the fibres leads to improved damping of a fibre reinforced composite under transverse normal oscillations. Large shear deformations occur in the coating material since its stiffness is very low in comparison with that of the fibre and matrix.

In this paper it has been shown how a micro- and mesomodelling methodology in concert with only a few simple DMTA measurements can be utilized to model the macroscopic stiffness response of an impacted beam at various temperatures and loading rates. The material models used for simulation of the material show a good correlation with the experimental data despite the exclusion of a damage model and failing to account for the temperature variation within the specimens used in the experimental testing. The peak loads are well predicted.

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